

LEVEL OF ACTIVITY, STRENGTH, AND SPASTICITY OF LOWER-LIMB MUSCLES AMONG VARIOUS TYPES OF SPINAE BIFIDA: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Spina bifida causes different degrees of lower limb muscle activity, strength, and spasticity based on the nature of the lesion. These impairments impact the mobility and functional outcomes, although there is limited comparative data on various types of spinae bifida.

Objective: To evaluate differences in lower limb muscle strength and spasticity and functional mobility among children diagnosed with various types of spina bifida in Peshawar.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was carried out at the Physical Therapy Department of Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar, which included ninety-two children aged 1 month to 3 years. Muscle strength, spasticity, and functional mobility were evaluated using the method of manual muscle testing (MMT), the Tardieu Scale, and the Gross Motor Function Classification System (GMFCS). Data Analysis was performed by using SPSS version 25.

Results: Among 92 participants, 78.3% (72) were males and 21.7% (20) were females. Significant differences were observed between spina bifida types across all functional parameters ($p < 0.001$). Findings indicated that the children with spina bifida occulta demonstrated better muscle strength, less spasticity, and higher mobility. While children with meningocele and myelomeningocele showed weaker muscle strength, increased muscle tone and higher functional limitations. Correlation Analysis showed that the muscle strength was closely associated with increased spasticity and reduced mobility.

Conclusion: The degree of functional limitation among children with Spina Bifida varies according to the lesion type. Timely detection along with standardized assessment using MMT, GMFCS and The Tardieu Scale can help clinicians in developing personalized strategies, improving mobility, and supporting long term independence.

INTRODUCTION:

Spina Bifida is a congenital condition that occurs when the spine and spinal cord fail to develop completely during the early weeks of gestation. The literal meaning of the term is "Split Spine," which refers to the incomplete closure of the neural tube.(1) When this closure does not occur properly defects

develop in the vertebral column and the neural tissues leading to different level of neurological impairments.(2) Spina Bifida is considered one of the most common type of neural defects and it can be mild to severe depending on the level of involvement of spinal cord.(3) Three main types of spina bifida are 1: spina bifida occulta, 2:

meningocele, 3: myelomeningocele. Myelomeningocele represents the most severe and functionally significant presentation. (4). Globally, the prevalence of spina bifida ranges from approximately 0.5 to 8 per 1,000 live births, with noticeable variations across different regions depending on socioeconomic settings (5). Some studies also show report of a slightly higher occurrence in females as compared to males (6).

Early management begins soon after birth and includes surgical closure of the spinal defect to reduce the risk factor of infection and limit further neurological deterioration (7). Although surgical techniques have improved over time, many children continue to experience long term complications such as motor weakness, sensory deficits, and bowel or bladder dysfunction. With timely surgical intervention, consistent rehabilitation and appropriate assistive support, many children with spina bifida can lead active and meaningful lives; however, the degree of independence achieved largely depends on the extent of neurological impairments.

Since spina bifida mainly affects the spinal cord, it frequently causes motor dysfunctions and neuromuscular impairments below the level of the lesion, ranging from mild weakness to total paralysis (8,9). Therefore, creating individualized treatment and rehabilitation plans requires a precise assessment of motor function. To test different elements of movement and motor control in these individuals, clinical examination techniques such as the Tardieu Scale, the Gross Motor Function Classification System, and Manual Muscle Testing (MMT) are frequently used (10).

The Tardieu Scale, GMFCS, and MMT are three evaluation instruments that provide distinct perspectives on various facets of motor function. When combined, they offer a comprehensive clinical approach for evaluating people with spina bifida (11). Muscular strength is measured by MMT, global motor ability is categorized by GMFCS, and the Tardieu Scale aids in distinguishing between mechanical and spastic limitations (1). This all-encompassing strategy guarantees precise progress records, permits customized

rehabilitation, and supports clinical judgment for both conservative and surgical treatments (12).

For children with spina bifida, doctors can maximize therapy, minimize secondary problems, and encourage meaningful involvement in school and community activities by identifying functional limits early and routinely evaluating them using these standardized tests (13).

Rationale:

The International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) framework is being used more often in physical therapy practice for children with spina bifida, despite variations in clinical presentations. This is because it draws attention to participation restrictions (like social engagement), activity limitations (like walking limitations), and impairments (like muscle weakness and stiffness) (14).

Mobility guidelines and objective evaluation methods help doctors monitor progress and tailor interventions to each patient's needs, promoting the greatest possible functional results and quality of life. In order to provide important information for appropriate physical therapy interventions and enhance mobility outcomes in this group, this cross-sectional study is to examine the degree of activity, strength, and spasticity of lower limb muscles among different forms of spina bifida.

METHODOLOGY:

• **Objectives:**

To assess and compare the level of activity, muscle strength, and spasticity in lower limb muscles among patients with different types of spina bifida in Peshawar.

• **Study design**

The study design that was used in this study was a cross-sectional study design.

• **Study Population/Setting**

The spina bifida patients and the study setting was Physical Therapy Department of Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar because it is a tertiary healthcare with high caseload of pediatric neurological conditions.

• **Sampling Technique**

Non-probability convenience sampling

technique was used in this study.

- **Sample Size**

The sample size was calculated by the Raosoft Sample Size calculator software. The total population size was 120 (Assuming one patient visits the OPD each day, with 4 weeks in a month and a total duration of 6 months, there would be $6 \times 4 = 24$ weeks. Considering 5 working days per week, the total number of patients would be $24 \times 5 = 120$) from which the calculated sample size was 92.

- **Study Duration**

Duration of this study was from Jun 2025 to November 2025.

- **Inclusion Criteria**

- Diagnosed cases of Spina Bifida (any type: myelomeningocele, meningocele, or spina bifida occulta) confirmed by medical records.

- Children aged 1 month to 3 years.

- Currently attending a rehabilitation center (e.g., physiotherapy, occupational therapy) in Peshawar.

- Psychiatrically stable

- Written and informed consent was obtained from parents and legal guardians. Age -and comprehension-appropriate assent was also obtained from the children.

- **Exclusion criteria**

- Children with co-existing neurological disorders unrelated to spina bifida (e.g., cerebral palsy, muscular dystrophy).

- Children with severe intellectual disability that prevents meaningful participation or assessment.

- Children who have undergone recent surgery (within the last 3 months) affecting motor function.

- Children who are not cooperative or unable to follow basic instructions during assessment.

- Incomplete medical records or diagnosis were not formally documented.

- **Data Collection Procedure**

After approval from the graduate committee (GC) and Advanced Studies and Research Board (AS&RB) and ethical committee of Khyber Medical University, permission for data collection was obtained from LRH hospital. After data collection permission, participants were screened for inclusion and

exclusion criteria. Those patients who were willing and fulfilling the inclusion criteria were given the information sheet. Written informed consent was taken from the patients. Data was collected by the primary researcher, using the GMFCS, Tardieu Scale, and MMT for assessing activity level, spasticity, and muscle strength.

- **Data Analysis Procedure:**

SPSS version 25 was used for the analysis of the study data. Frequencies and percentages were generated for categorical variables such as gender, socioeconomic status, and comorbidities, while the mean and standard deviation were calculated for continuous variables. The Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests were used to determine whether the key outcome measures, such as muscle strength, spasticity, and functional mobility, were normal. The data were deemed to be non-normally distributed since all variables displayed p-values less than 0.05. Therefore, for the following studies, non-parametric statistical approaches were used. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare group differences in muscle strength, spasticity, and functional mobility among the various forms of Spina Bifida. The Kruskal-Wallis H test was used in comparisons involving more than two groups. Because muscle strength, spasticity, and functional mobility were ordinal in character, Spearman's rank-order correlation was used to assess associations between them.

The 0.01 and 0.05 levels were used to determine correlation strength and significance. The Chi-square test was used to examine relationships between categorical variables, such as the kind of Spina Bifida and outcomes related to disability. Fisher's Exact Test was used when anticipated cell numbers were inadequate. Two-tailed tests were used for all statistical methods, and the threshold for statistical significance was set at a p-value of less than 0.05.

- **Ethical Consideration:**

Proposal for study was presented to and accepted by the Advanced Studies & Research Board, the Institutional Graduate Committee and the Institutional Ethical Committee. Following approval, study participants were

chosen from the study settings and after being fully informed about the study’s purpose and methodology, written informed consent was obtained.

RESULTS:

Table 1: Gender Distribution of Participants

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	72	78.3%
Female	20	21.7%
Total	92	100%

• **Descriptive Statistics of Outcome Variables**

Descriptive statistics for lower limb muscle strength, spasticity, and functional mobility are presented in Table 2. The mean muscle strength score measured using Manual Muscle Testing (MMT) was 2.84 ± 1.53 , indicating moderate variability in muscle strength among

• **Participant Characteristics**

A total of 92 children diagnosed with spina bifida were included in the study. Among them, 72 (78.3%) were male and 20 (21.7%) were female (Table 1).

participants. The mean spasticity score measured using the Tardieu Scale was 2.10 ± 1.56 , suggesting mild to moderate levels of spasticity. Functional mobility assessed through the Gross Motor Function Classification System (GMFCS) showed a mean level of 2.29 ± 1.23 .

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Muscle Strength, Spasticity, and Functional Mobility

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
Muscle Strength (MMT)	2.84	1.53
Spasticity (Tardieu Scale)	2.10	1.56
Functional Mobility (GMFCS)	2.29	1.23

• **Normality Testing:**

The Shapiro-Wilk test was performed to assess the normality of the primary outcome variables. All variables demonstrated

significant deviation from normal distribution ($p < 0.05$), therefore non-parametric statistical tests were applied for further analysis.

Table 3: Shapiro-Wilk Test for Normality

Variable	Statistic	p-value
Muscle Strength (MMT)	0.919	<0.001
Spasticity (Tardieu Scale)	0.896	<0.001
Functional Mobility (GMFCS)	0.862	<0.001

• **Comparison Across Types of Spina Bifida**

The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare muscle strength, spasticity, and functional

mobility among the three types of spina bifida: spina bifida occulta, meningocele, and myelomeningocele.

Table 4: Mean Ranks of Functional Outcomes According to Type of Spina Bifida

Variable	Type of Spina Bifida	N	Mean Rank
Muscle Strength (MMT)	Spina Bifida Occulta	32	76.50
	Meningocele	43	38.23
	Myelomeningocele	17	10.94

Spasticity (Tardieu Scale)	Spina Bifida Occulta	32	18.89
	Meningocele	43	57.00
	Myelomeningocele	17	71.91
Functional Mobility (GMFCS)	Spina Bifida Occulta	32	16.50
	Meningocele	43	54.00
	Myelomeningocele	17	84.00

Table 5: Kruskal-Wallis Test Results

Outcome Variable	H Statistic	df	p-value
Muscle Strength (MMT)	77.727	2	<0.001
Spasticity (Tardieu Scale)	58.806	2	<0.001
Functional Mobility (GMFCS)	83.156	2	<0.001

The Kruskal-Wallis analysis demonstrated statistically significant differences among the three types of spina bifida in muscle strength, spasticity, and functional mobility ($p < 0.001$).

• **Correlation Analysis**

Spearman’s rank-order correlation was used to examine the relationships among muscle strength, spasticity, and functional mobility.

Table 6: Spearman’s Correlation Between Muscle Strength, Spasticity, and Functional Mobility

Variable	Muscle Strength	Spasticity	Functional Mobility
Muscle Strength	1	-0.720**	-0.896**
Spasticity	-0.720**	1	0.748**
Functional Mobility	-0.896**	0.748**	1

Note: $p < 0.01$

Muscle strength demonstrated a strong negative correlation with spasticity ($\rho = -0.720$) and functional mobility limitation ($\rho = -0.896$). Spasticity showed a positive correlation with functional mobility limitation ($\rho = 0.748$).

• **Pairwise Comparison Between Spina Bifida Occulta and Meningocele**

The Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare children with spina bifida occulta and meningocele.

Table 7: Mann-Whitney U Test for Functional Variables

Outcome Variable	Mann-Whitney U	p-value
Muscle Strength (MMT)	0.001	0.001
Spasticity (Tardieu Scale)	0.001	0.001
Functional Mobility (GMFCS)	0.001	0.001

Table 8: Mean Rank Comparison (Occulta vs Meningocele)

Variable	Spina Bifida Occulta (Mean Rank)	Meningocele (Mean Rank)
Muscle Strength	59.50	22.00
Spasticity	16.50	54.00
Functional Mobility	16.50	54.00

The Mann-Whitney U test indicated statistically significant differences between the two groups, with children with spina bifida occulta demonstrating greater muscle strength and better functional mobility, while children

with meningocele showed higher levels of spasticity and mobility limitations.

DISCUSSION:

The cross-sectional study described the lower

limb strength, spasticity, and functional mobility of 92 children with spina bifida between the ages of 1 month to 3 years of age by adopting the MMT, Tardieu Scale and GMFCS. The early impairment was moderate, and Krustal-Wallis tests demonstrated the existence of highly significant differences between occulta, meningocele and myelomeningocele with occulta having rather preserved strength and functioning and myelomeningocele with the highest compromise, which agrees with the previous studies that relate open lesions to the worse motor outcome and the most limited ambulation (15). Evidence of differences in strength, spasticity and mobility also existed when comparing only non-myelomeningocele subtypes, which confirms the importance of anatomical subtype as a key factor of prognosis when used with other modifiers that are already known to determine outcomes, including motor level, hydrocephalus and orthopedic deformities (16, 17). The differences in birth order in the sample probably were due to the local family structure and not a real etiologic or prognostic effect.

Correlation studies revealed that strength, tone and mobility are strongly correlated: weaker children were more spastic and less mobile and increased spasticity was linked with worse gross motor performance. These results are consistent with evidence that lower limb strength, specifically that of the quadriceps and hip muscles, is closely associated with ambulation status and performance in the most important gross motor skills in spina bifida (18, 19) and that muscle tone and strength are significant to ambulatory status and independence. The same strength-function-QOL relationships have been simulated in spastic cerebral palsy, with weakness and spasticity affecting gross motor activity, mediating health related quality of life (20). Collectively, these data indicate that functional limitations and the strength-spasticity-function interaction are predetermined in early childhood.

The clinical implications of the research are that standardized measures of strength and tone (e.g. MMT and Tardieu) should be routinely used at an early age, pragmatic

functional classifications (e.g. GMFCS) may be more useful than disease specific tools (e.g. Dias functional classification, Peds NRS, Myelomeningocele Functional Classification) in reflecting spina bifida motor capacity and walking activity (20, 21). The fact that strength is closely related to mobility supports the hypothesis behind early, strength focused physiotherapy that strengthening can promote improved functional recovery but does not increase spasticity in cerebral palsy and that progressive resistance training increases mobility in spina bifida (21). The findings though cross sectional and single center give useful early life functional benchmarks by subtype and underscores the importance of longitudinal multidimensional assessment to inform individualized rehabilitation to optimise ambulation, independence and long-term quality of life.

- **Strengths:**

This study provides important insights into the functional activity levels, stiffness, and strength of lower limb muscles in children with various forms of spina bifida. Functional evaluation is more accurate and reliable when several clinical parameters are assessed using standardized instruments such the Gross Motor Function Classification System (GMFCS), Tardieu Scale, and Manual Muscle Testing (MMT). Targeted rehabilitation planning is made easier by early detection of muscle performance and mobility limitations, which helps to avoid secondary problems and improve long-term functional outcomes.

- **Limitations:**

Although these advantages, some drawbacks need to be recognized. The non-probability convenience sampling technique used in the study may have limited the findings' applicability to the larger spina bifida community. Even while the sample size is sufficient for descriptive analysis, it might not accurately reflect the range of clinical presentations, particularly within age groups and lesion levels. The cross-sectional design limits the capacity to monitor longitudinal outcomes after therapeutic interventions or track functional changes over time. Furthermore, variables that may also affect strength, spasticity, and mobility outcomes

such as cognitive status, comorbid diseases, dietary status, and access to rehabilitation services were excluded.

• **Conclusion:**

Significant differences in lower limb muscle strength, stiffness, and functional mobility across children with various forms of spina bifida are highlighted in this study. According to the research, children with spina bifida typically have moderate muscle weakness and movement impairments, with the degree of spasticity varying according to the degree of neurological involvement. These findings highlight the variety of functional impairments present in this population and highlight how crucial early clinical evaluation is to promoting tailored rehabilitation programs. A thorough profile of motor function is produced by combining the use of standardized clinical instruments such the Tardieu Scale, MMT, and GMFCS. This profile can help direct physical therapy planning and improve functional outcomes.

Children with spina bifida might benefit from early physiotherapy management that uses standardized evaluation measures to increase independence and avoid problems, thereby improving their quality of life.

• **Future Directions:**

To improve generalizability, future research should employ multicenter settings with larger sample sizes. To find out how muscle strength, spasticity, and mobility vary over time, longitudinal study is advised. Additionally, to maximize the functional result for children with spina bifida, the efficacy of early and targeted rehabilitation interventions could be assessed using standardized and objective outcome measures.

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